

season and on about 30,600 ha in the 1976–77 wet season.

IR26 was first reported to be damaged by the BPH in September 1976. In February 1977 hopperburn was confirmed in IR26 and IR34, and IR30 was severely attacked (see photo). At three locations, IR32 appeared resistant; at one location, IR36 seemed resistant. The highest BPH populations (adults + nymphs/hill) were 1,008 on IR26, 1,508 on IR30, 47 on IR32, 18 on IR34, and 40 on IR36. Most of the insects were in the first and second instars, except for two cases of more advanced insect development on IR26. No hill in 11 fields was found infected with symptoms of grassy stunt; 24% infection was observed in 1 field. On December 15, 1976, the Extension Service of the N. Sumatra provincial government estimated the total area of rice fields attacked as 43,618 ha, with 3,482 ha of hopperburn. On 31 January 1977, 43,783 ha of BPH damage was reported, with 7,597 ha of hopperburn. About 9,400 ha of the damage and 880 ha of the hopperburn were on IR26. This was the first report of large areas of IR26 being severely attacked by the BPH in Indonesia. ❧

Population fluctuation of brown planthopper in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* is a major rice pest in Kerala. Its first reported outbreak was in the punja crop of 1973–74. It caused extensive damage in Kuttanadu, Alleppey district, and in the Kole areas of Trichur district.

These rice-growing tracts are waterlogged and the fields must be drained after the monsoon rains for paddy cultivation. Rice is extensively grown, mostly as a monoculture crop. After one or two rice crops, the fields remain under water for the rest of the year. Notable features of rice cultivation in these areas that may favor the BPH are widespread cultivation of susceptible high yielding varieties, such as Jaya and IR8; high

seeding rates; excessive nitrogen use; indiscriminate insecticide application, which causes destruction of natural enemies; and favorable climatic factors.

The Rice Research Station, Moncompu, concentrates its efforts on the BPH problem through a multidisciplinary approach. To study the population fluctuations, we have recorded light-trap catches of BPH in Kuttanadu since January 1974.

The population peaks twice each year, in each cropping season. The maximum catch was recorded from January to March, with the highest peak in February. Interestingly, this peak coincides with the booting and postflowering stages of the main crop (Oct.–Nov. to Feb.–Mar.). Hopperburn and serious crop losses are common during this period. The BPH population begins to decline by late March when the harvest ends and continues to drop until July. The next peak is from July to September, during the autumn crop. But because of adverse climatic conditions, such as heavy rains and high winds, the population does not rise to alarming proportions during this period, and so the crop is safe. The light-trap studies also show that BPH are present throughout the year. Survival of the pest during the off-season, when there is no standing crop, should be further investigated. ❧

Varietal resistance to the rice thrip, *Baliothrips biformis*

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Baliothrips biformis is primarily a pest of seedling paddy which emerges in the drier months and infests the late-planted crops in both crop seasons in Sri Lanka. Depending on the degree of infestation, the insect can retard growth or kill the seedling. Breeding for thrip resistance would be the most economical means of control. Of the almost 800 indigenous varieties that underwent preliminary observation, those that showed reasonably good levels of resistance were field-tested in replicated trials

during the 1976 and 1977 dry seasons. Damage was observed at 2 weeks after seeding or at the 3- to 4-leaf stage. The system of evaluation was as follows.

Reaction ¹	Damage
R	Leaves remained healthy except for very slight rolling of the first and second leaf.
MR	Slight rolling and withering of the first and second leaf.
MS	First and second leaf withered and dead; upper leaves slightly rolled.
S	Upper leaves rolled, withered, and with few white lesions; lower leaves dead.
HS	Upper leaves dying with pronounced white lesions, seedlings are stunted; lower leaves dead.

¹R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Varieties found resistant and moderately resistant to the pest are listed below.

Variety	Reaction
Dahanala 2220	R
Dahanala 682	R
Kaluheenati 547	R/MR
Heenati 896	MR
Mudukiriyal 197	MR
Kalubalawee	MR
Demalakotan 1630	MR
Gonabaru	MR/MS

Serious attacks of rice gall midge in the central plain of Thailand

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has long been one of the most important rice pests in northern and northeastern Thailand, but not in the central rice-growing area. In June 1977, however,